

Donor Behavior of Trithiocarbodiglycolic Acid with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

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Complexes of trithiocarbodiglycolic acid (LH₂) with bivalent metal ions of the formulae [ML(H₂O)₂] (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}) and [CuL(H₂O)] have been prepared and characterised by magnetic moment, ir and electronic spectral data.

The complexes of a number of thiocarboxylic acids and polythiocarboxylic acids are known^{1,2}. Trithiocarbodiglycolic acid (LH₂) is known since long³ but for the first time we report the complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with (LH₂).

Results and Discussion

Trithiocarbodiglycolic acid (LH₂) forms complexes of composition [ML(H₂O)₂] (M = Co²⁺, Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺ or Cd²⁺) and [CuL.H₂O] (Table 1). Except [CuL(H₂O)], other complexes are stable in solid state. Copper(II) complex gradually decomposes in light yielding brownish black product of indefinite composition.

The TGA curves in static air with heating rate of 10°/min of the Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes ML(H₂O)₂ show that the complexes are quite stable below 40–45° and starts losing weight around 50° gradually but the loss in weight is rapid at 60–70°. The weight-loss at 100–110° is 55% for Cd^{II} and 64% for Zn^{II} complexes. The TGA curve shows that the product is stable below 280–290° and decomposes to constant weight at 290–300°. The residual weight of the complexes corresponds to metal sulphide. The residual product gives H₂S gas with dil. HCl which substantiates it as metal sulphide. The weight-loss at 100–110° corresponds to the formation of equal amount of metal sulphide and metal thioglycolate. The weight-loss around 40–45° indicates that water is either weakly bonded to metal or present as lattice water forming hydrogen bond with sulphur atom.

In case of the Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, the TGA curves show that weight-loss is gradual but they completely decompose at 300–320° to constant weight. The weight of the product indicates that the residue is not completely metal sulphide but a mixture of metal oxide and metal sulphide as well. The Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes are quite stable in air but lose water molecules slowly above 90–110° and become anhydrous at 150° with appreciable change in colour and in magnetic moment values (Table 1) indicating that water molecules are coordinated in aquo-

complexes [ML(H₂O)₂], {M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} or Ni^{II}}. In general, these complexes are almost insoluble in benzene, ethanol and methanol, but dissolve in DMF and water. The aqueous solutions of the Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes slowly decompose yielding insoluble precipitates of metal sulphides.

Magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra : As expected the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic while others are paramagnetic. The room temperature magnetic moment values of the Co, Ni and Mn complexes (Table 1) occur in the range of octahedral environment of ligand molecules around metal atoms⁴. Freshly prepared copper(II) complex displays magnetic moment value of 1.81 B.M. indicating that [CuL(H₂O)] is magnetically dilute.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis(%) : Found/(Calcd.)	
			Metal	S
[MnL(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	5.91	17.56 (17.41)	30.16 (30.51)
[CoL(H ₂ O) ₂]	Buff	5.01	18.30 (18.46)	29.83 (30.14)
[NiL(H ₂ O) ₂]	Green	3.24	18.18 (18.41)	29.39 (30.16)
[CuL(H ₂ O)]	Green	1.89	20.65 (20.14)	30.73 (31.47)
[ZnL(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	Dia	20.14 (20.06)	28.18 (29.54)
[CdL(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	Dia	30.08 (30.16)	25.24 (25.82)
[MnL]	Yellow	5.94	19.43 (19.69)	—
[CoL]	Brown	4.93	20.61 (20.80)	—

* At 304–05 K.

In methanolic solution, LH₂ exhibits a medium absorption band at 23810 cm⁻¹ and an intense band at 32787 cm⁻¹, assignable to $n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions respectively. The solid as well as the aqueous solution of the metal complexes display the former band near 23250 cm⁻¹. The $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the ligand almost disappears in the complexes on coordination. In addition to ligand absorption near 23250 cm⁻¹, the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes exhibit two ligand

field bands in the visible region. In the Ni^{II} complex [NiL(H₂O)₂], a weak band at 14930 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) and a shoulder near 24390 cm⁻¹ to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P) transitions in weak octahedral field⁶. A weak band at 18870 cm⁻¹ in the Co^{II} complex [CoL(H₂O)₂] is assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) and a shoulder near 22220 cm⁻¹ to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(P) transitions⁶ respectively. In these diaquo-metal chelates [ML(H₂O)₂] (M = Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Mn²⁺ or Cu²⁺) the ligand (LH₂) appears to be dianionic quadridentate molecule and water molecules to be coordinated with metal atom. In aqueous solution of the cobalt(II) complex no appreciable change in band position could be detected. However, in case of the Ni^{II} complex [NiL(H₂O)₂] the band at 14930 cm⁻¹ is raised to a higher energy in aqueous solution and observed at 16950 cm⁻¹. The increase in the energy of ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) transition indicates some structural changes and most probably tetra-aquo species [NiL(H₂O)₄] has been formed in aqueous solution. The ligand field parameters (10 Dq and β) calculated by the method of Lever⁷ using relations of ν₂ and ν₃ transitions for solid complexes, have been found to be 10 Dq = 9322 and β = 763 cm⁻¹ for [NiL(H₂O)₂] and 10 Dq = 8810 and β = 824 cm⁻¹ for [CoL(H₂O)₂]. The values of 10 Dq of the complexes indicate that ligand is fairly weak. The nephelauxetic ratio β of the Ni^{II} complex (0.73) is fairly low. The low value of β for Ni^{II} is characteristic of 'S' coordination of the ligand⁸ in the complex [NiL(H₂O)₂]. Freshly prepared [CuL.H₂O] displays a broad band at 13160 cm⁻¹ assignable to E_g → T_{2g} transition⁹ in approximately octahedral field.

Ir spectra : The ligand displays OH stretch as broad band at 2890 and 2590 cm⁻¹ indicating the involvement of the carboxylic OH group in hydrogen bonding. In the complexes, ν_{OH} disappears indicating the deprotonation of the carboxylic OH group in bond formation. The hydrated complexes display a broad and strong absorption at 3300–3450 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} of water molecules. The –CH₂– stretches of the ligand are observed at 2942 and 2900 cm⁻¹ as sharp bands, and these are observed as weak bands or shoulder in the complexes. The ligand displays ν_{as}(COO) at 1630 and ν_s(COO) at 1330 cm⁻¹ as broad and strong bands. In the complexes, the ν_{as}(COO) band is shifted to lower frequencies by 50–60 cm⁻¹ while the ν_s(COO) band is raised to higher frequency by 25–50 cm⁻¹. The separation of ν_{as}(COO) and ν_s(COO) of the free ligand (300 cm⁻¹) is reduced to 180–225 cm⁻¹ in its metal complexes, indicating that both carboxylic oxygens are involved in bonding either by coordination or in hydrogen bonding through coordinated or lattice water molecule¹⁰. The –CH₂– scissoring and ν_{C-C} vibrations of the ligand are observed at 1200 and 1040 cm⁻¹ which are not affected appreciably in the complexes, but found to be splitted into two bands in some complexes.

The ν_{C=S} band of the free ligand is observed at 870 cm⁻¹ (strong and broad) which is raised to higher frequency by 12–15 cm⁻¹ in almost all the complexes, indicating that

thiocarbonyl sulphur is not involved in coordination^{11,12}. The ligand displays shoulders at 820 and 780 cm⁻¹ attributable to ν_{-CH₂-} out-of-plane bending and ν_{C-S} band respectively. The ν_{C-C} is shifted to lower frequencies by 10–20 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. The lowering of ν_{C-S} band suggests the coordination of ether sulphur to metal atoms in complexes similar to polythiodiacetic acids and *s*-methylthiosalicylic complexes with bivalent metal ions^{1,2,13}. The broad and medium band at 700–675 cm⁻¹ is attributed to ρ_w(H₂O) of coordinated water molecules¹⁰.

Hence, it is inferred that the ligand is bonded to the metal atom through carboxylic oxygens and ether sulphurs of ligand molecules as well.

Experimental

Trithiocarbodiglycolic acid was prepared as reported in the literature³. The product was crystallized from hot ethanol.

Metal complexes. [ML_nH₂O] (M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}) : Methanolic solution of the metal acetate (0.01 mol) in aqueous methanol (50 ml) was added with stirring to the ligand (0.015 mol) dissolved in methanol on a steam-bath. The complex separated gradually was filtered, washed with excess of methanol and dried in air. The dried sample was found quite stable at room temperature. The complexes on prolong standing in aqueous methanol (2–3 days) decomposed giving metal sulphide.

Magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectra were recorded as reported earlier¹⁴. TGA was performed on a Stanton Red Craft TG-750 thermobalance with a heating rate of 10°/min with chart speed of 120 mm/h in static air.

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